

INTERLAYERS IN LAMINATES : MODELING AND INFLUENCE ON THE FREE-EDGE EFFECTS

M. Haboussi *1,2* , H. Dumontet *1*, J. L. Billoët *1*

*1 Laboratoire de Modélisation et de Mécanique des Structures
CNRS UPRES A n° 8007 , ENSAM/UPMC/ENSC
151, Boulevard de l'Hôpital 75013 Paris*

*2 Laboratoire d'Energetique et de Mécanique Théorique et Appliquée
CNRS UMR n° 7563, INPL/ENSEM/EEIGM
ENSEM - 2, av. de la Forêt de Haye
B.P. 160 - 54504 Vandoeuvre Cedex*

SUMMARY: The problem of free edge effects is examined with a special emphasis on the interlayer modelling. Currently observed in such materials, the interlayer is constituted by a resin enrichment and a specific fiber distribution which confer to the interlayer a continuous/diffuse behavior. Realistic models have then been developed in order to describe the transition behavior due to the interlayer in laminated composite. Based on a spatial continuous function, the first model permits the description of an evolutive transition behavior which relates continuously the adjacent layer behaviors. The second kind of models proposed uses interface laws which are defined on material surfaces (with no thickness). Developed on the basis of matched asymptotic analysis, these laws are equivalent to the transition evolutive behavior primarily obtained. Used in a numerical analysis, these different models permit to show the influence of the interlayer on free-edge effect analysis.

KEY WORDS: Interfacial region, transition behavior, matched asymptotic method, laminates, free-edge effects, stress concentration, singularity.

INTRODUCTION

As seen in the figure 1, interlayers in laminates may include, besides the fibres specific distribution, a resin enrichment. In a precedent work, Haboussi & al. (1997, 1998), we saw that the perfect interface model is not able to incorporate the physical reality of the interlayer. So, we proposed an evolutive model to describe the transition behavior of the interlayer. The pertinence of such model in giving a relevant evaluation of the free-edge effects was demonstrated. Indeed, the interface interlaminar stress distributions obtained were not singular at the free edge and satisfy better the boundary conditions compared to the perfect interface results. Nevertheless, this model only takes into account the specific distribution of fibres at the interlayer, and hence, neglects the resin enrichment.

In this paper, other models which take into account the resin enrichment are proposed. Our interest is motivated by the fact that many experimental observations give to the resin enrichment a role in the delamination mechanisms, Johannesson & al. (1984), Whitney (1989), Llanos & Vizzini (1992).

The first kind of model is a spacial evolutive model. Based on a continuous function, it permits to describe the continuous/diffuse behavior of the interlayer due to the resin enrichment and the specific distribution of fibers at the interlayer. The second kind of models consists on interface laws asymptotically equivalent to the evolutive model when the small

thickness of the interlayer is neglected compared to the total thickness of the adjacent layers. These laws are obtained by using matched asymptotic analysis, Cole & Kevorkian (1980), Leguillon (1995). The interface laws depend on the interlayer thickness and also on the interlayer relative rigidity compared to those of the adjacent layers. The interlayer rigidity depends itself on the resin enrichment.

Implemented in the finite element software ABAQUS, the different models have been used in a free-edge effects analysis on a $(0^\circ/90^\circ)$ s laminates submitted to uniform traction presenting either a flexible or a rigid diffuse interlayer.

Fig. 1: Cross section of $(0^\circ/+65^\circ/-65^\circ/0^\circ)$ laminate, Lilholt and Andersen (1992).

After presentating, in paragraph 2, the evolutive models developed for a rigid and flexible diffuse interlayer, we describe, in paragraph 3, the various equivalent interface laws obtained by the matched asymptotic method from the original models. Paragraph 4 concerns the numerical treatment of the different models and the free edge effects applications.

TRANSITION BEHAVIORS FOR THE INTERLAYER

In order to estimate the elastic properties of the interlayer, we have analysed the fiber distribution by using a classical notion in granular mechanics; the wall effect. This analysis is based on the fact that the distribution of fiber volume fraction is not stochastic at the vicinity of the interlayer (wall). It is "quasi-determinist" and may be approximated by the function illustrated in Fig. 2 :

Fig. 2 : Approximation of the fibre volume fraction distribution through a bimaterial thickness due to the wall effect (D_f is the fibre diameter)

The fiber volume fraction varies from zero at the wall and reaches its average value along a distance approximately equal to the fiber diameter size. The interlayer thickness is about twice the diameter value (without taking the resin enrichment thickness in account).

This fiber distribution leads to an evolutive behavior as seen in Fig. 3 for the elastic properties C_{1313} and C_{2323} . The complete elastic tensor for the interlayer can be approximated by the following mathematical function :

$$C^c(x_3) = \begin{cases} C^r + \frac{2x_3}{e} (C^+ - C^r) & 0 \leq x_3 \leq +\frac{e}{2} \\ C^r - \frac{2x_3}{e} (C^- - C^r) & -\frac{e}{2} \leq x_3 \leq 0 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Fig. 3: Distribution of the elastic properties due to the wall effect through the composite thickness

where C^r represents the resin elastic properties, C^+ and C^- , those of the adjacent layers. e indicates the dimensionless thickness of the interlayer (the ratio of the interlayer thickness to the total thickness of the adjacent layers).

If we consider the resin enrichment, the interlayer property function becomes :

$$C^c(x_3) = \begin{cases} C^r + 2\frac{C^+ - C^r}{1-\delta} \left(\frac{x_3 - \delta}{e} - \frac{\delta}{2} \right) & \frac{\delta e}{2} \leq x_3 \leq +\frac{e}{2} \\ C^r & -\frac{\delta e}{2} \leq x_3 \leq \frac{\delta e}{2} \\ C^r - 2\frac{C^- - C^r}{1-\delta} \left(\frac{x_3 + \delta}{e} + \frac{\delta}{2} \right) & -\frac{e}{2} \leq x_3 \leq -\frac{\delta e}{2} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where δe is the resin enrichment thickness, δ representing the proportion of the resin enrichment in the interlayer. The case of δ tending towards 0 corresponds to an interlayer with a poor enrichment in resin (rigid behavior). Whereas the case of δ tending towards 1, corresponds to an interlayer “strongly” enriched in resin (flexible behavior). In this case, the resin elastic properties are considered under the form :

$$C^r = \tilde{C}^r e \quad (3)$$

where \tilde{C}^r is a rigidity tensor of the same order of magnitude as C^+ or C^- , the dimensionless thickness e of the interlayer (lower than 1), is also a structural parameter and corresponds to the relationship between the rigidity of the resin and that of the adjacent layers.

The interface laws developed for each one of these two cases are presented in the following paragraph.

EQUIVALENT INTERFACE LAWS

An asymptotic analysis of the transmission elasticity problem through an interlayer of very small thickness, whose evolutive behavior is successively rigid (1) and flexible (2)-(3), has been carried out by means of the matched asymptotic method. This technique consists in seeking the displacement solution of the elasticity problem pertaining to the composite structure containing an interlayer with a small thickness e under the following form :

$$U^e(x_1, x_2, x_3) = U^0(x_1, x_2, x_3) + eU^1(x_1, x_2, x_3) + e^2U^2(x_1, x_2, x_3) \dots \quad (4)$$

(x_1, x_2) are the plane coordinates of the composite. The strain $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(U)$ and thus the stresses \mathbf{s} are also developed as functions of the small parameter e .

After replacing these developments in the elasticity equations and satisfying the perfect adherence boundary and matched behavior conditions at the top and the bottom of the interlayer, different partial/intermediate elasticity problems are identified at different orders. Solving these problems at different orders allows us to get successive interface laws.

RIGID INTERFACE LAW

The equivalent interface law for the rigid evolutive behavior (1) is given by :

at the first order :

$$[\sigma_{i3}^0] = 0 ; [U_i^0] = 0 \quad i=1,2,3 \quad (\text{interface conditions of perfect adhesion}) \quad (5a)$$

complemented at the higher order by :

$$[U_\alpha^1] = \Im(\sigma_{\alpha 3}^0(x_1, x_2, \rho) \mathcal{C}_{\alpha 3 \alpha 3}^\pm \mathcal{C}_{\alpha 3 \alpha 3}^r) \quad (5b)$$

$$[U_3^1] = \Re(\sigma_{33}^0(x_1, x_2, \rho) \varepsilon_{33}^0(x_1, x_2, \rho^\pm) \varepsilon_{\alpha\beta}^0(x_1, x_2, \rho^\pm) \mathcal{C}_{3333}^\pm \mathcal{C}_{33\alpha\beta}^\pm \mathcal{C}_{3333}^r) \quad (5c)$$

$$[\sigma_{\alpha 3}^1] = \aleph \left(\frac{\partial \sigma_{\alpha 3}^0}{\partial x_3}(x_1, x_2, \rho^\pm) \frac{\partial \varepsilon_{\alpha\beta}^0}{\partial x_\beta}(x_1, x_2, \rho^\pm) \mathcal{C}_{\alpha\beta 33}^\pm \mathcal{C}_{3333}^\pm \mathcal{C}_{\alpha\beta 33}^r \mathcal{C}_{3333}^r \right) \quad (5d)$$

$$[\sigma_{33}^1] = 0 \quad (5e)$$

The symbols $[.]$ indicate the jump condition of the quantity considered at the interface $[f] = f(x_1, x_2, \rho^+) - f(x_1, x_2, \rho^-)$. The symbols $\Im \Re \aleph$ indicate functions depending on the variables placed between brackets. These functions are not explicitated because of their complexity. (cf (Haboussi, 1998) for the detail of the asymptotic analysis).

So, when the resin rate of the interlayer is not important, its rigid behavior is equivalent to an asymptotic law which is constituted, at the first order, by the perfect conditions of adherence and is complemented, at the following order, by jump conditions of imperfect adherence expressed on displacements and stresses. The complementary conditions of transmission are established to correct the model of perfect interface which is supposed idealizing the joining between the adjacent layers. Similar analysis have been carried out by Ngueteng & Sanchez (1985), Leguillon (1995) for an homogeneous isotropic medium containing a thin layer homogeneous and isotropic too.

FLEXIBLE INTERFACE LAW

The equivalent interface law for the flexible evolutive behavior (2)-(3) is given by :

at the first order :

$$\left[\sigma_{i3}^0 \right] = 0 \quad (6a)$$

$$\sigma_{i3}^0 = \frac{\tilde{C}_{i3}^r}{\delta} \left[U_i^0 \right] \text{ (without summation on } i) \quad (6b)$$

This interface law is complemented by the non interpenetrability physical condition of materials in compression state,

$$\sigma_{33}^0 < 0 \Rightarrow \left[U_3^0 \right] = 0 \quad (6c)$$

When the resin enrichment of the interlayer is important, its equivalent behavior is equivalent to an interface law expressed by condition of imperfect adhesion which relates the stress traction at the interface between layers to the possible relative displacement vector through stiffness coefficients. These coefficients depend on the resin properties and the resin enrichment thickness. This law is completed by a non-interpenetrability consistency condition to avoid the non physical phenomena of material penetration observed in numerical applications.

Similar results were obtained in the case of a flexible homogeneous and isotropic interlayer (representing an adhesive layer) by many authors among them, Klarbring (1991), Destuynder & al. (1992), Geymonat (1996).

Interface laws which proportionally relate stress vector to jump conditions are also adopted to simulate an imperfection adhesion or decohesion and slip mechanisms at the interface between two media Benveniste (1985), Hashin (1991), Cheng & al. (1996). The stiffness coefficients intervening in these models are imposed as being the ratio of the resin/adhesive properties on the fictitious/real thickness of the interlayer.

These interface laws as well as the evolutive models have been implemented numerically in the finite element software ABAQUS in order to analyse free edge effects in a laminate.

APPLICATIONS TO FREE EDGE EFFECTS ANALYSIS

STUDIED PROBLEM

The studied problem is the basic uniform tensile test of a $(0^\circ/90^\circ)_S$ laminate presenting an interlayer. Analysis of the free-edge stresses will be performed first by using an evolutive modeling of the interlayer in two configurations : a rigid interlayer (without resin enrichment) and a flexible interlayer (with a resin enrichment). The equivalent interface laws (rigid and flexible) will then be used instead of the evolutive behavior.

Fig. 4 : $(0^\circ/90^\circ)$ laminate in traction and its meshed part

The layers are considered transversely isotropic, with the following characteristics in full mass :

$$E_{11} = 38250 \text{ MPa}; E_{22} = E_{33} = 9200 \text{ MPa}$$
$$G_{23} = 3135 \text{ MPa}; G_{13} = G_{12} = 3770 \text{ MPa}; \nu_{12} = \nu_{13} = 0.325$$

The resin properties are : $E = 3500 \text{ MPa}$, $\nu = 0.35$

FREE EDGE EFFECTS WITH EVOLUTIVE BEHAVIORS (RIGID AND FLEXIBLE)

The discretisation of the laminate, realised on ABAQUS, uses a cubic finite element meshing with only one element in the direction of loading in so far as the solution of the studied problem is independent from this direction. To simulate the continuous behavior of the interlayer, several ranges of finite elements in order to discretise the interlayer. At each range, different elastic properties values were introduced according to the behavior law; (1) for rigid interlayer and (2)-(3) for flexible interlayer. A linear interpolation of the behavior is then run during the calculation. The elements are gradually refined at the vicinity of the interlayer and free-edge.

In figure 5, we have illustrated the distribution of the normal interlaminar stress at the interface $(0^\circ/90^\circ)$ obtained for rigid (without resin enrichment, $\delta=0$) and flexible (with resin enrichment, $\delta=0.5$) interlayer. In the same figures, we have represented the stress distributions obtained by using a perfect interface model (This model is also a first order approximation of the rigid evolutive behavior).

At the free-edge, we observe that the magnitudes of the $(0^\circ/90^\circ)$ interlaminar stress concentrations are sensitive to the model used for the interlayer. The perfect interface model overestimates it whereas the other models give lower values which are different for each model. The lowest value corresponds to the flexible interlayer. These numerical observations well corroborate with experimental observations, (Johannesson & al., 1984), (Llanos &

Vizzini, 1992) concerning the relaxing role of resin enrichment on interlaminar stresses. From the numerical point of view, the stresses obtained when using the evolutive law are not singular whereas they are singular when using the perfect interface model. Otherwise, the different models also show that the interlaminar stresses vanish far from the free edge where there are no free edge effects.

Fig. 5: Normal interlaminar stress along the interface ($x_3=h$) with an expansion at the vicinity of the free-edge

In the next section, we shall examine the free edge evaluations by using the equivalent interface laws, i.e. by replacing the evolutive behavior discretisation by interface finite elements.

FREE EDGE EFFECTS WITH THE RIGID INTERFACE LAW

We have already noted that at a great distance from the free edge, the rigid evolutive behavior and the perfect interface model corroborate. These numerical results agree with the asymptotic analysis because the perfect interface model is a first order approximation of the rigid evolutive behavior of the interlayer (5a). We have seen that the main differences between both models appear at the free edge on the maximum of interlaminar stresses. The question now is : are the correctors, given by the higher order conditions of the interface laws (5b-5e), able to correct the perfect interface model to reach the rigid evolutive law results at the free edge? This is the subject of the following section.

The calculation of the higher order stress correctors ($e\sigma^l$) requires the numerical implementation of the interface law (5). Thus, displacement jumps, fig. 6, calculated from (5a and 5c) have to be imposed upon the interface ($0^\circ/90^\circ$). We note that this calculation uses the perfect interface results. The numerical implementation was carried out on ABAQUS, (cf (Haboussi, 1998) for complementary details).

Figure 7 shows the normal component of the stress corrector vector along the interface ($0^\circ/90^\circ$) calculated on the two faces of the latter. The contribution of these correctors far from the free edge being very weak (tending to zero), well confirms the fact that the model of perfect interface is a first order approximation of the behavior of the rigid interlayer. However, at the intersection of the interface and the free edge, the stress correctors do not improve the perfect interface results. The use of several meshing refinements shows that these correctors are singular in that area. Indeed, the fact of imposing discontinuity displacement

conditions at the interface, calculated from interface stresses whose evolutions are singular at the free edge, naturally leads to a singular problem at this point, (Leguillon, 1995). So, the stress correctors for this problem are not able to correct the first order approximation of perfect interface to incorporate the influence of local transition behavior in accurately evaluating the interface interlaminar stresses at the free edge. However, they confort the asymptotic result which states that the perfect interface model is a first order approximation of the rigid evolutive behavior.

Fig. 6: Displacement correctors jumps at the interface ($0^\circ/90^\circ$)

Fig.7 : Distribution of the normal stress corrector at the interface

FREE EDGE EFFECTS WITH THE FLEXIBLE INTERFACE LAW

The calculation of free-edge using the flexible interface law requires also the realisation of a finite interface element authorizing the weak slip and decohesion between bonded joint layers and ensuring the non interpenetration condition, Haboussi (1998).

The flexible interface law is the equivalent law to the evolutive behavior of an interlayer whose thickness and rigidity are weak compared to the thickness and the rigidity of the adjacent layers. To demonstrate this numerically on the free edge problem, we have used different small thicknesses and elastic properties of the interlayer in the numerical simulations (When the interlayer is thinner, it is also more flexible). In the same curve, Fig. 8, we illustrate the interlaminar stresses obtained for various flexible interlayer thicknesses with the same proportion of resin enrichment ($\delta=0.5$) using the equivalent flexible interface law

(designed by FIL on the graphs). We can see that the interlayer stress distributions converge towards the results obtained with the imperfect flexible interface law when the interlayer is becoming smaller and more flexible. The imperfect interface law thus advantageously replaces the flexible evolutive behavior of the interlayer, when its thickness becomes very small. The use of increasingly refined meshings shows that the interlaminar stresses obtained by both modelings of the flexible interlayer are not singular at the free edge and the interface intersection.

Fig. 8: Normal interlaminar stress distributions using evolutive flexible behaviors and their equivalent interface law

CONCLUSIONS

This work shows the influence of the interlayer on free-edge effects. Two types of interlayer (rigid and flexible) depending on resin enrichment proportion have been examined. The interface stress concentrations at the free-edge are found less important when the interlayer contains significant amount of resin enrichment.

Different models have been proposed to describe the interlayer behaviors. They consist either of a spatial behavior models or their equivalent zero thickness interface laws. The interface laws have been obtained by matched asymptotic analysis. Their numerical implementation gives us interface finite elements in ABAQUS. The various numerical results confirm the asymptotic analysis and shows that the use of interface finite elements allows for an effective and low-cost simulation of the evolutive interlayer behavior.

REFERENCES

- 1- H. Lilholt, S. I. Andersen, "Suppression of multiple cracking in $(0^\circ/+65^\circ/-65^\circ/0^\circ)$ carbon fibre/epoxy laminates", *ECCM 5 France*, Eds A. R. Bunsell, J. F. Jamet, A. Massiah, p. 359-364, 1992.
- 2- M. Haboussi, H. Dumontet, J. L. Billoët, "Interface modelling in laminated composites for free-edge effect analysis", *International Conference of Composite Materials*, Gold Coast, Australia, Ed Murray L. Scott, p. 453-463, 1997.

- 3- M. Haboussi, H. Dumontet, J. L. Billoët, "Proposal of refined interface models and their application for free-edge effect", *Composite Interfaces*, 1998 (in press).
- 4- T. Johannesson, P. Sjöblom, R. Selden, "The detailed structure of delamination fracture surfaces in graphite/epoxy laminates", *Journal of Materials Science*, 19,
- 5- J. M. Whitney, "Experimental characterization of delamination fracture", *Composite Materials 5*, Series editor R. B. Pipes, Elsevier, 1989.
- 6- A. S. Llanos, A. J. Vizzini, "The effect of film adhesive on the delamination strength of tapered composites", *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 26, No. 13, p. 1968-1983, 1992.
- 7- J. D. Cole, J. Kevorkian, "Perturbation methods in applied mathematics", Springer., New-York, 1980.
- 9- D. Leguillon, "Concentration de contraintes et rupture dans les joints adhésifs", *Actes du Colloque national en calcul des structures de Giens*, Ed Hermès, p. 107-112, 1995.
- 10- M. Haboussi, "Contribution à la modélisation de l'intercouche dans les stratifiés composites : application aux effets de bords libres", Thèse de doctorat de l'Ensam de Paris, Mars 1998.
- 11- N. Nguetseng, E. Sanchez-Palencia, "Stress concentration for defects distributed near a surface", In *local Effect in the Analysis of Structures* (Edited by P. Ladevèze), p. 55-74, Elsevier, 1985.
- 12- A. Klarbring, "Derivation of the model of adhesively bonded joints by the asymptotic expansion method", *Int. J. Engng. Sci.* , Vol. 29, No. 4, p. 493-512, 1991.
- 13- P Destuynder, F. Michavila, A. Santos, Y. Ousset, "Some theoretical aspects in computational analysis of adhesive lap joints", *Int. Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering*, vol. 35, p. 1237-1262, 1992.
- 14- G. Geymonat, F. Krasucki, S. Lenci, "Analyse asymptotique du comportement d'un assemblage collé", *C. R. Acad. Sci. Paris*, t. 322, p. 1107-1112, 1996.
- 15- Y. Benveniste, "On the effect of debonding on the overall behavior of composite materials", *Mech. Mater.*, Vol. 3, p. 349-358, 1985.
- 16- Z. Hashin, "Thermoelastic properties of particulate composites with imperfect interface", *J. Mech. Phys. Solids*, Vol. 39, 6, p. 745-762, 1991.
- 17- Z. Cheng, A. K. Jemah, F. W. Williams, "Theory for multilayered anisotropic plates with weakened interfaces", *Journal of Applied Mechanics*, Vol. 63, p. 1019-1026, 1996.